

SEISMIC ANALYSIS OF MULTISTORIED BUILDING WITH AND WITHOUT VERTICAL MASS IRREGULARITY

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ABSTRACT:

The sudden slip at the fault, planar fracture or discontinuity in a volume of rock, across which there has been significant displacement as a result of rock mass movement, causes the earthquake a violent shaking of the Earth during which large elastic strain energy released spreads out in the form of seismic waves that travel through the body and along the surface of the Earth. Structures designed for gravity loads, in general, may not be able to safely sustain the effects of horizontal earthquake shaking. Hence, it is necessary to ensure adequacy of the structures against horizontal earthquake effects. There are many studies carried out about earthquakes but however it has not been possible to predict when and where earthquake will happen. In this study, 3D Analytical model of G+15 storeyed buildings have been generated for vertical mass irregularity. Three models are generated with difference in vertical mass irregularity analysed by using analysis tool 'ETABS Non-linear Version 9.5.0'. The parameters considered in this paper are fundamental time period, base shear and displacement. The analysis is done with two different methods namely linear static Method (Equivalent Static Method) and Linear Dynamic Analysis (Response Spectrum Analysis). In this study, the displacements values are increasing as the irregular mass shifts towards top. The base shear values are considerably high in buildings having vertical mass irregularity and as the vertical mass shifts towards top, base shear decreases.

KEYWORDS: Seismic waves, Vertical Mass irregularity, ETABS, linear Static method, Linear Dynamic method.

INTRODUCTION:

Irregular buildings constitute a large portion of the modern urban infrastructure. Structures are never perfectly regular and hence the designers routinely need

to evaluate the likely degree of irregularity and the effect of this irregularity on a structure during an earthquake. About 90% of all earthquakes result from tectonic events, primarily movements on the faults (Agrawal and Shrikhandeet al., 2006). Structures designed for gravity loads, in general, may not be able to safely sustain the effects of horizontal earthquake shaking. Hence, it is necessary to ensure adequacy of the structures against horizontal earthquake effects (C. V. R. Murty et al., 2002). Need for research is required to get economical and efficient lateral stiffness system for high seismic prone areas. For optimization and design of high rise building with different structural framing systems subjected to seismic loads. The innovative and revolutionary new ETABS is the ultimate integrated software package for the structural analysis and design of buildings. From the start of design conception through the production of schematic drawings, ETABS integrates every aspect of the engineering design process. Creation of models has never been easier - intuitive drawing commands allow for the rapid generation of floor and elevation framing.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The R.C.C and Composite structures with one of the important consideration of Mass irregularity in the form of swimming pool at 9th floor, Equivalent static and Response spectrum methods are used to analyse the building as per IS 1893(Part1):2002 using SAP 2000 software. The study shows that Composite structures having mass irregularity will better perform than R.C.C. structures. Design base shear values are reduced by 18% for composite structures. The dead weight of the composite structures is less compared to R.C.C. structures by 18%, hence earthquake forces also reduced by 18%. Shear force in Composite structures is reduced by 20%. Results obtained for Equivalent static method for R.C.C and composite structures are quite high than Response spectrum method (Cholekar & Basavalingappa et al., 2015). Reinforced cement

concrete building of G+10 having mass irregularity in 3rd and 6th floors and building without mass irregularity are analysed. It was observed that there is an increase of 67% in the moments of mass irregular buildings than buildings without mass irregularity. Size of the structural members also increases for buildings with mass irregularity (N.Anvesh, Yajdani and Pavankumar et al., 2015). Different irregularity and torsional response due to plan and vertical irregularity and to analyse cross shape and L shape building while earthquake forces acts and to calculate additional shear due to torsion in the columns. From the torsion point of view the re-entrant corner columns must be strengthen at lower floor levels and top two floor levels and from the analysis it is observed that behaviour of torsion is same for all zones. Effect of torsion is much more when diaphragms at some level are removed, so in re-entrant corner building it is better to avoid irregularity in diaphragm (Modakwar, Meshram and Gawatre et al., 2014). The seismic performance of G+6 storey regular and irregular Reinforced Concrete (RC) buildings using ETABS (V. 9.7.1), to evaluate the impact of vertical irregularity on RC buildings in terms of static linear-Equivalent Static Lateral force Method (ESLM) and nonlinear analysis (PUSHOVER). Maximum base shear occurs in the mass irregularity building as compared to other models. Maximum lateral displacement is obtained mass irregular building and less in vertical geometric irregularity building shows less displacement (Pathi, Guruprasad, Dharmesh and Madhusudhana et al., 2014). Building model of G+ 5 storey, the building models are studied for vertical geometric irregularity in seismic zone V of India. Steel bracings are provided on the outer periphery of the models on all the four sides and analysed. Types of bracings considered for the study are X-type, V-type and K-type bracing. Lateral displacement and Storey drift increases as the amount of irregularity present in the building increases. Addition of bracings to the bare frames shows reduction in lateral displacement and storey drift (Karthik and Vidyashree et al., 2015). Modelling of the building for five different systems viz. unbraced frame, Chevron Braced Frame, Eccentrically Braced Frame, Single Diagonal Braced Frame and X Braced Frame under same loading conditions is done using ETABS. From comparative study, we conclude that introducing bracing system increase lateral stiffness and improve seismic performance of the building. Use of Chevron braced frame system is more efficient than any other braced frame system (Odedra and Tarachandani et al., 2016). The effect of mass irregularity on different floor in RCC buildings with as Response Spectrum analysis was performed on regular and various irregular buildings using Staad-Pro. It was found that mass

irregular building frames experience larger base shear than similar regular building frames (Khan and Dhamge et al., 2016).

MODELLING:

The Reinforced Concrete building models used in this study is G+15 storied, have same floor plan with 5m bays along longitudinal direction and 4.5m bays along transverse direction as shown in figure 1. The storey height is 3m for all the stories. The live load taken has 3 KN/m² for all floors and no live load on roof, while the floor finish load is taken as 1 kN/m² on all other floors. Thickness of brick wall over all floor beams is taken as 0.230 m. Thickness of slab is taken as 0.15 m. The unit weight of reinforced concrete is 25kN/m³ and brick masonry is taken as 20 kN/m³. The compressive strength of concrete is 25 N/mm² and yield strength of steel reinforcements is 415 N/mm². The modulus of elasticity of concrete and steel are 25000 N/mm² and 2×10⁵ N/mm² respectively. All the structures have been considered to be located in seismic region V with an importance factor 1 and sub-soil type 2 (medium) and response reduction factor 5 (SMRF).

MODEL 1 – Regular building

MODEL 2 – Regular building with heavy mass on 6th floor.

MODEL 3 – Regular building with heavy mass on Roof.

The model is prepared of G+15 Storey. The regular building model is without mass irregularity as shown in figure 1. The model 1 regular building is as shown in figure 2. Heavy mass, it is taken as SIL (Superimposed Load) 20 KN/m² on 6th floor and on RF (Roof) as shown in figures 3 and 4 respectively.

Fig 1: ETABS MODEL

Fig 2: ETABS MODEL 1

Fig 3: ETABS MODEL 2

Fig 4: ETABS MODEL 3

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Results of the building models studied are presented and discussed in detail. The results of fundamental natural period of vibration, lateral displacements and storey drifts are included for building models and compared. The fundamental time period of models is tabulated in table 1 and graph of model v/s time period is as shown in graph 1.

Table 1: Fundamental Time period of buildings

	TIME PERIOD (sec)
MODEL 1	2.4837
MODEL 2	3.2642
MODEL 3	3.4990

Graph 1: Model v/s Time period

The Base shear of models is tabulated in table 2 and graph of model v/s Base shear is as shown in graph 2.

Table 2: Base shear

MODEL 1		MODEL 2		MODEL 3	
Fx	Fy	Fx	Fy	Fx	Fy
3603.2	3612.7	4959.56	4408.09	4612.27	4136.17

Graph 2: Model v/s Base shear

The Storey displacement in X-direction of Models (Linear static analysis) of models is tabulated in table 3 and graph of model v/s storey displacement is as shown in graph 3.

Table 3: Storey displacement in X-direction of Models (Linear static analysis)

STORY	MODEL 1 DISP-X	MODEL 2 DISP-X	MODEL 3 DISP-X
RF	54.19507	64.56399	67.35597
15	53.20627	63.601	65.65396
14	51.64134	61.9493	63.29944
13	49.46588	59.54315	60.35951
12	46.7363	56.43894	56.88597
11	43.52077	52.71848	52.86658
10	39.87491	48.4538	48.21096
9	35.84453	43.67317	43.09535
8	31.99713	39.09357	38.31236
7	28.03158	34.33579	33.41995
6	23.94743	29.39769	28.43592
5	19.78218	24.30186	23.39884
4	15.59072	19.13965	18.36855
3	11.45412	14.034	13.43743
2	7.501022	9.160235	8.756389
1	3.951328	4.802704	4.585579
GF	1.203389	1.455263	1.388285

Graph 3: Storey v/s Displacement

The Storey displacement in Y-direction of Models (Linear static analysis) of models is tabulated in table 4 and graph of model v/s storey displacement is as shown in graph 4.

Table 4: Storey displacement in Y-direction of Models (Linear static analysis)

STORY	MODEL 1 DISP-Y	MODEL 2 DISP-Y	MODEL 3 DISP-Y
RF	58.61781	87.18903	91.35678
15	57.66702	86.08871	89.23102
14	56.07082	84.02141	86.20736
13	53.84127	80.96229	82.44241
12	51.05447	77.01954	78.02651
11	47.78766	72.31332	72.94607
10	44.11156	66.95616	66.99073
9	40.0976	61.0488	60.53099
8	36.2902	55.42598	54.52776
7	32.29223	49.49337	48.31896
6	28.13076	43.25476	41.93873
5	23.84728	36.67984	35.43155
4	19.47883	29.91762	28.84036
3	15.06011	23.0689	22.20907
2	10.63054	16.21473	15.5966
1	6.271914	9.504475	9.13672
GF	2.279935	3.426833	3.292923

Table 6: Storey displacement in Y-direction of Models
(Response spectrum analysis)

STORY	MODEL 1 DISP-Y	MODEL 2 DISP-Y	MODEL 3 DISP-Y
RF	40.07488	53.56794	57.85442
15	39.5371	53.01913	56.71389
14	38.64017	52.00448	55.12022
13	37.38501	50.50767	53.15582
12	35.80747	48.57065	50.84935
11	33.93728	46.2258	48.13753
10	31.79618	43.49689	44.79197
9	29.40249	40.40882	41.08048
8	27.06382	37.38441	37.55791
7	24.52499	34.08953	33.8176
6	21.78041	30.45695	29.85468
5	18.83881	26.3372	25.68328
4	15.70729	21.90264	21.31801
3	12.39177	17.24365	16.76385
2	8.909706	12.38927	12.03028
1	5.335778	7.422934	7.198911
GF	1.959594	2.733338	2.648098

Graph 4: Storey v/s Displacement

The Storey displacement in X-direction of Models (Response spectrum analysis) of models is tabulated in table 5 and graph of model v/s storey displacement is as shown in graph 5.

Table 5: Storey displacement in X-direction of Models
(Response spectrum analysis)

STORY	MODEL 1 DISP-X	MODEL 2 DISP-X	MODEL 3 DISP-X
RF	36.45179	48.26687	52.25426
15	35.87936	47.67066	51.11141
14	34.98041	46.64899	49.55946
13	33.73423	45.16265	47.64609
12	32.16918	43.23842	45.38269
11	30.31259	40.90465	42.70074
10	28.17323	38.17391	39.44137
9	25.72464	34.9995	35.72518
8	23.30124	31.84843	32.15561
7	20.74946	28.49881	28.44992
6	18.04016	24.89147	24.5928
5	15.17609	20.98471	20.58939
4	12.18006	16.84448	16.4649
3	9.105157	12.58943	12.2787
2	6.056933	8.374914	8.157594
1	3.233128	4.47411	4.354207
GF	0.995156	1.382066	1.344131

Graph 5: Storey v/s Displacement

The Storey displacement in Y-direction of Models (Response spectrum analysis) of models is tabulated in table 6 and graph of model v/s storey displacement is as shown in graph 6.

Graph 6: Storey v/s Displacement

CONCLUSION:

More mass means higher inertia force. Therefore, lighter buildings sustain the earthquake shaking better. The vertical acceleration during ground shaking either adds to or subtracts from the acceleration due to gravity. Since factors of safety are used in the design of structures to resist the gravity loads, usually most structures tend to be adequate against vertical shaking. ETABS is an integrated analysis, design and drafting of buildings systems tool. ETABS dynamic analysis capabilities include the calculation of vibration modes using Ritz or Eigen vectors, response-spectrum analysis and time history analysis for both linear and nonlinear behaviour. According to the results, it is

concluded that the fundamental natural time period of the building increases with the increase in vertical mass irregularity. The base shear values (i.e. F_x and F_y) are considerably high in buildings having vertical mass irregularity and as the vertical mass shifts towards top, base shear decreases. Displacement values of buildings with vertical mass irregularity are more compared to the regular building. The displacements values are increasing as the irregular mass shifts towards top.

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REFERENCES:

- 1) C. V. R. Murty (2002) National Information Centre of earthquake engineering at IIT Kanpur <<https://www.nicee.org/EQTips.php>>
- 2) ETABS <<https://wiki.csiamerica.com/display/etabs/Home>>
- 3) N. Anvesh, Dr. Shaik Yajdani, K. Pavan Kumar, Effect Of Mass Irregularity On Reinforced Concrete Structure Using Etabs (2015), ISSN(Online) :2319-8753, ISSN (Print) : 2347-6710 International Journal Of Innovative Research In Science, Engineering And Technology (An ISO 3297: 2007 Certified Organization) Vol. 4, Issue 10, October 2015 Pp 10091-10096, DOI:10.15680/IJRSET.2015.0410055
- 4) Pankaj Agrawal, Manish Shrikhande (2006). Earthquake Resistant Design Of Structures, PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd., India
- 5) Karthik. K. M, Vidyashree. D, Effect Of Steel Bracing On Vertically Irregular R.C.C Building Frames Under Seismic Loads 2015, International Journal Of Research In Engineering And Technology E-ISSN: 2319-1163 P-ISSN: 2321-7308 Volume: 04 Issue: 06 Pp 90-96
- 6) Mr. Pathan Irfan Khan, Dr. Mrs. N. R. Dhamge (2016), Review Paper On Seismic Analysis Of Multistoried Rcc Building Due To Mass Irregularity, International Journal Of Science & Engineering Development Research, ISSN : 2455-2631, June 2016 IJSDR, Volume 1, Issue 6 PP 428- 431
- 7) Neha P. Modakwar, Sangita S. Meshram, Dinesh W. Gawatre, IOSR Journal Of Mechanical And Civil Engineering, Seismic Analysis Of Structures With Irregularities (2014), (IOSR-JMCE) E-ISSN: 2278-1684, P-ISSN: 2320-334 . PP 63-66
- 8) Nuthan L Pathi, Guruprasad T N, Dharmesh N And Madhusudhana Y.B, Static Linear And Non-Linear (Pushover) Analysis Of Multi Storey Rcc Frame With And Without Vertical Irregularities (2014), International Journal Of Science, Engineering And Technology Research ISSN-2278-7798.
- 9) Odedra Chirag R., Deepak Tarachandani (2016), Comparative Study Of Effect Of Structural Irregularities & Different Types Of Bracings In Multistoried Steel Building, IJSRD - International Journal For Scientific Research & Development| Vol. 4, Issue 03, 2016 | ISSN (Online): 2321-0613 Pp 547-552
- 10) Prof. Swapnil B. Cholekar, Basavalingappa S. M., Comparative Analysis Of Multistoried Rcc And Composite Building Due To Mass Irregularity (2015), International Research Journal Of Engineering and Technology E-ISSN: 2395 -0056 Volume: 02 Issue: 04 | July-2015 Pg 354- 365.